

Multirate Control Strategies for avoiding samples losses.

Julian Salt, Jose Alcaina

*Systems Eng. and Control Dept., Instituto de Automatica e Informatica Industrial,
Universitat Politecnica de Valencia, Cno. Vera, s/n, E-46022 VALENCIA, SPAIN.
e-mail: {julian,joalac}@isa.upv.es*

Abstract

When in a digital control schema there are samples lost due to diverse limitations, one solution is to assume different options: Inferential (IC) and Multirate Control (MR) are known. The objective of this contribution is to introduce various viable schema in this environment and to answer to some usual questions about them. Is better an inferential control or a multirate control?. It is used a new efficient algorithm for computing a multirate system frequency response for these control structures. The performance and disturbance effects are studied in detail and some interesting results are reported.

Keywords: Inferential Control, Model-Based, Dual-rate systems, frequency response, stability, Bode diagram

1. Motivation

In the field of automatic control, since the seminal papers from [1, 2, 3, 4] the multirate sampled-data system (MR) have been considered in a wide variety of applications. Chemical analyzers [5], visual feedback [6], low-cost sensors [7], and more recently applied to networked based control [8]. A MR can be defined as a hybrid system composed of continuous time elements, usually the plant, and some discrete time components, usually the controllers and/or the filters, where two or more variables are sampled or updated at different frequencies. If there are only two sampling frequencies, the system is called dual-rate (DR) and an important practical case is the MRIC (multirate input control), that is characterized by an slow output and a fast input, where an integer relation between them and a regular pattern of sampled signals without sampling times mismatch are usually considered.

Figure 1: Fast Digital Control

In the contribution [9] a simple inferential schema is assumed if it is not possible to obtain the output sampled with a certain frequency. In some applications it is not viable to consider this frequency for updating the control action because the performance degradation or even the instability risk. This is a typical MRIC case and one of the easiest control proposals is to fill in the fast lost samples with samples delivered by a model. This is a model based inferential control. The problem becomes when the model uncertainty is deep enough. In this contribution, it is attempted to compare with some other strategies in frequency domain taking advantage of a new tool that allow to compute the frequency response for DR systems in an efficient way [10].

The work is structured as follows. First some comments about sampled data frequency techniques and a brief review of DR modeling and frequency response is introduced. With this knowledge, it will be possible to model every schema and consequently to study its frequency characteristics. Finally some interesting consequences about disturbance rejection and reference tracking will be exposed.

2. Problem Statement

The problem to solve is originated in a classical digital control at sample period T . With some process model $G_p(s)$ and some desired performance, a controller $G_R(z)$ is designed by any suitable direct or indirect method (where variable z stands for the LTI-transform argument at sampling period T). In these conditions the control schema is depicted in figure 1. In order to compare with the other options in this paper, this control will be called "fast" control.

As it was already said, if due to different reasons, it is not possible to have access to all output samples Y^T , then different options can be considered.

Figure 2: Inferential Control

Basically two options will be analysed: the first one is what is known as dual-rate inferential control used in industrial applications [5] and showed in figure ??.

In figure 2 the sampling of the output is effective each T/N being $N \in \mathcal{N}$. this situation has been described using a variable λ defined as:

$$\lambda = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } t = kT/N \quad k \in \mathcal{Z} \\ 0 & \text{if } t \neq kT/N \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

λ represents a kind of switch that allows to get real samples if $\lambda = 1$ or samples delivered by a model in the other case. Obviously a linear periodically time varying system is met. It is called DR in the sense that two frequencies appears $1/T$ and N/T .

A classical DR solution is introduced in figure 3 where the output is sampling each NT (described by Y^{NT}) but the control is updated every T (U^T) that is N times faster. To handle this solution, an special controller must be designed. This non-conventional structural controller is composed by a slow part G_1^{NT} , a digital hold that repeats N times the slow controller output,

$$H^{T,NT} = \frac{1 - z^{-N}}{1 - z^{-1}}$$

and a fast controller G_2^T . There are different ways to design this Dr controller. From the easiest one, that consists in assuming $G_1^{NT} = 1$ and preserves the fast controller $G_R(z)$ for G_2^T , with imprevisible behaviour or more elaborated design procedures (see for instance [8]). In this work, the MR model-based controller will be assumed [11]. Basically, if $M(s)$ represents the desired close loop performance of the original continuous system design, the DR design with:

$$G_1^{NT} = \frac{1}{1 - M(z^N)}$$

Figure 3: Dual-Rate Control

, and

$$G_2^T = M(z)/G_p(z)$$

where $M(z)$ and $M(z^n)$ are the $M(s)$ discretized with ZOH for periods T and NT respectively. This procedure leads to a behaviour that matches perfectly $M(s)$ in the sample points but can (due to the magnitude of NT) introduce a ripple between samples. The way to overcome this, also described in [11], is to consider:

$$G_2^T = G_R(z)/(1 + G_R(z) * G_p(z))$$

Therefore the DR controller does not cancel the numerator of the process transfer function avoiding the ripple.

3. Lifting Modeling

As it was exposed, some alternatives are going to be checked. A fast T digital control, an inferential DR control and a classical DR control schema. The last two options introduce a linear periodically time varying discrete-time system. The original idea was introduced by [1]. It was called Vector Switch Decomposition (svd). In figure 4 is exposed an open loop DR system in which the input and output sequences are assumed to have different sampling periods, T_u and T_y (it is assumed) that they are rationally related. In figure 5 the application of svd to this case is depicted considering there exist integers N_u , N_y such that $T_0 = T_u N_u = T_y N_y$ (indeed, then $T_u/T_y = N_y/N_u$ is a rational number) being $T_0 = lcm(T_u, T_y)$. This metaperiod T_0 is the repetition period of every sequence in this scenario. In figure ??, the case where $T_u = T$ and $T_y = NT$ is exposed. With this conditions it is easy to introduce the discrete-lifting operator that will allow to transform a MR schema into a T_0 single rate problem. This technique was explained in contributions like [] Figure 4 depicts an open loop DRS and figure 5 describes the application

Figure 4: Generalized dual-rate System

Figure 5: Kranc vector switch decomposition

of Kranc's idea vector switch decomposition to the situation of figure 4. In the sequel it is explained briefly the basic idea with the intention that this perspective helps to understand the discrete lifting. If $r(t)$ is a continuous signal, with Laplace transform $R(s)$, its sampling at period T_i leads to the discrete sequence $r(kT_i)$ which \mathcal{Z} function will be noted by R_i^T . In these conditions the Kranc's idea was to propose:

$$R^{T/N} = R^T + (e^{sT/N} R)^T e^{-sT/N} + \dots + (e^{sT(N-1)/N} R)^T e^{-sT(N-1)/N}$$

So, it is possible to express:

$$R^{T/N} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & e^{-sT/N} & \dots & e^{-s(N-1)T/N} \end{bmatrix} \left(\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ e^{sT/N} \\ \vdots \\ e^{s(N-1)T/N} \end{bmatrix} R \right)^T \quad (2)$$

As it can be seen in figure 5 it is introduced the notation:

$$V^{N+} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ e^{sT/N} \\ \vdots \\ e^{s(N-1)T/N} \end{bmatrix}$$

and DECIR QUE EL INFERENCIAL SE HA EMPAQUETADO A NT !!!!!

$$V^{N-} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & e^{-sT/N} & \dots & e^{-s(N-1)T/N} \end{bmatrix}$$

Therefore:

$$R^{T/N} = V^{N-} \left(V^{N+} R \right)^T$$

formula which is the representation of the T/N sampler decomposition into N branches including a new T (lcm) sampler. In the general case is being treated:

$$(1 \ z^{-N_y} \ \dots \ z^{-(N_u-1)N_y}) \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ e^{sN_y} \\ \vdots \\ e^{s(N_u-1)N_y} \end{bmatrix} R \right\}^{T_0} = V_z^{N_u-} (V^{N_u+} R)^{T_0} \quad (3)$$

where, as it is reminded, z stands for gcd period T and T_0 is the lcm of all sampling periods involved in the general schema. In equation (3) the subindex z represents the substitution $z = e^{Ts}$. According to this procedure, the schema in figure 5 can be described by:

$$Y^{T_y} = V_z^{N_y^-} \tilde{G} \left(V_z^{N_u^+} U \right)^{T_0}$$

and \tilde{G} is what is said the T_0 lifted matrix. Note that every signal is lifted in a T_0 sampling frame. It is usual to model the behaviour of the DRS characterised via a “lifted” transfer function matrix:

$$y_l(z^N) = \tilde{G}(z^N)u_l(z^N) \quad (4)$$

If the block G between samplers (it could be a continuous process plus zero order hold) is a SISO LTI system, the system in figure 4 is clearly a shift varying discrete-time system. At [?] is probed that $\tilde{G}^{T_0} = V_z^{+N_y} G V_z^{-N_u}$ is LTI N_u input N_y output shift invariant. This correspondence between periodic and expanded LTI system preserves both the analytic and algebraic properties of the systems [?]. In particular, block-diagram algebra procedures could be considered.¹ In the next section it will be introduced this algebra to model the periodic systems to compare.

At this point it is important to point out that in [13?] links between external and internal representation are established.

4. Closep Loops Lifted Models

In this section, the block-diagram algebra is used to expose the models of the closed loops to check assuming lifted signals. Obviously it is not necessary to obtain the fast digital control lifted model. In figures 6 and 8 are depicted the DR and inferential control respectively considering such procedure. Considering these figures and the procedure explained graphically, it is possible to express the lifted input-ouput relation for the DR loop (5) and for the Inferential DR Loop (6)

¹It must be noted that it is also possible to define the lifted scheme from a discrete system, but obviously the input sampling period will be the same that the applied to the system

Figure 6: Kranc vector switch decomposition

Figure 7: Kranc vector switch decomposition

Figure 8: Kranc vector switch decomposition

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{U} &= KG_2^{N_2, N_2} * KG_1^{N_1, N_2} [\mathbb{1}_{\alpha_1 \times \alpha_2} + KG_p^{N_2, N_3} Cx_{N_3, N_1}]^{-1} \\ Y^{T/N_3} &= KG_p^{N_2, N_3} \bar{U} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $\alpha_1 \times \alpha_2$ are the size of the product $KG_p^{N_2, N_3} Cx_{N_3, N_1}$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{U}_R &= KG_R^{N_2, N_2} [\mathbb{1}_{\beta_1 \times \beta_2} + \tilde{K}G_p^{N_2, N_3} Cx_{N_3, N_2}]^{-1} \\ Y^{T/N_3} &= \tilde{K}G_p^{N_2, N_3} \bar{U}_R \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

being $\beta_1 \times \beta_2$ are the size of the product $\tilde{K}G_p^{N_2, N_3} Cx_{N_3, N_2}$

Now, $\tilde{K}G_p^{N_2, N_3}$ is quite special because it is made up of two different parts which corresponds to the order of sampling in the switch of figure 2. If an example is considered, the understanding will be easiest. Take $N = 3$ and assume that just the first of N samples is picked up of the real process G_{pr} and the others $N - 1$ are delivered by the model G_{pm} . If both of them are second-order systems and described by a state representation A_r, B_r, C_r, D_r and A_m, B_m, C_m, D_m , then $\tilde{K}G_p^{N_2, N_2} \equiv A_t, B_t, C_t, D_t$ ²:

²a N_2, N_2 ia assumed in order to simplify the exposition

$$\begin{aligned}
A_t &= \begin{bmatrix} A_p & 0_{f,c} \\ 0_{f,c} & A_m \end{bmatrix} \\
B_t &= \begin{bmatrix} B_p \\ B_m \end{bmatrix} \\
C_t &= \begin{bmatrix} C_p(1,:) & 0_{f,c} \\ 0_{f,c} & C_m(2:N-1,:) \end{bmatrix} \\
D_t &= \begin{bmatrix} D_p(1,:) \\ D_m(2:N-1,:) \end{bmatrix}
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

where the sign ":" stands for "all" or for "begin to end" (like in Matlab®) and the zero matrices are of proper dimensions to get square matrices.

The next step is to introduce the DR frequency response for this kind of systems that have been modeled by a lifting procedure.

5. DRS frequency response computation

5.1. Preliminaries and notation

A dual-rate discrete LTI system is one in which the input and output sequences are assumed to have different sampling periods, T_u and T_y . If they are rationally related, it is possible to define the least common multiple $T_0 = lcm(T_u, T_y)$ usually known as "metaperiod" or "frame period" and there exist integers N_u, N_y such that $T_0 = T_u N_u = T_y N_y$ (indeed, then $T_u/T_y = N_y/N_u$ is a rational number). It is usual to define the "greatest common divisor sampling period" $T = gcd(T_u, T_y)$ as well, such that $T_0 = NT$ being $N = lcm(N_u, N_y)$; therefore $T_0 = NT = N_u T_u = N_y T_y$. With these conditions, the behaviour of the DRS may be characterized via a "lifted" transfer function matrix:

$$y_l(z^N) = G_{lifted}(z^N)u_l(z^N) \tag{8}$$

where the variable z stands for the LTI z -transform argument at sampling period T , and consequently z^N is related to $T_0 = NT$. In equation (8) y_l is a vector of length N_y , u_l is a vector of length N_u and G_{lifted} is a $N_y \times N_u$ transfer function matrix [12]. The lengths of the vectors are increased in the case of MIMO systems (multiplied by the number of outputs and inputs, respectively). Next figures can help to deduce and clarify completely this equation.

Note that in figure 5, $T_0/N_u = N_y T$ and $T_0/N_y = N_u T$. It is easy to see that with this scheme, the central part of the diagram would be:

$$(1 \ z^{-N_u} \ \dots \ z^{-(N_y-1)N_u}) \frac{G_{lifted}(z^{N_y N_u})}{N_y} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ z^{N_y} \\ \vdots \\ z^{(N_u-1)N_y} \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

At this point it is crucial to say that the discrete-lifted operators can be expressed in an external [?] or internal [13] representation. In the contribution [?] was described the links between both of them. Example???

5.2. Sampled-data lifted systems

There are different ways to obtain the lifted model. For processes, it may be the easier one is to consider the successive iterations from the gcd T discrete state space. If a strictly proper continuous system is discretised (assuming ZOH) at period T , with a realization $(A, B, C, 0)$, then the lifted dual-rate model has a realization (A_l, B_l, C_l, D_l) , at metaperiod T_0 , where these matrices are obtained by repeated evaluations of the equations at sampling period T giving rise to well-known convolution-like formulae. For instance:

$$\begin{aligned} y(kT_0 + \zeta T) &= Cx(kT_0 + \zeta T) = \\ &= C[A^\zeta x(kT_0) + A^{\zeta-1}Bu(kT_0) + \\ &+ A^{\zeta-2}Bu(kT_0 + T) + \dots + Bu(kT_0 + (\zeta - 1)T)] \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

for $\zeta = 1, \dots, (N_u - 1)N_y$. However, the zero-order-hold entails

$$\begin{aligned} u(kT_0 + dN_y T) &= u(kT_0 + (dN_y + 1)T) = \dots = u[kT_0 + ((d + 1)N_y - 1)T] \\ \forall d &= 0, 1, \dots, (N_u - 1) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Therefore the lifted matrices are obtained by suitably stacking the results from the above equation. It is also possible to consider that G has different nature (continuous system without ZOH, digital system, etc). For each of these cases a proper input or output assignments (like 11) must be established leading to a specific lifted model [13]. Some other details, omitted here for brevity, can be found in [12, 14, 15]. Now, a brief example could be considered. If in figure 4 G is a continuous-time plant with ZOH and $T_u = 0.3$

$y T_y = 0.2$ ($N_u = 2$ and $N_y = 3$), then the lcm $T_0 = 6$, the gcd $T = 0.1$, and the lifted representation will be:

$$\begin{aligned}
x[(k+1)T_0] &= A^6x(kT_0) + \begin{pmatrix} (A^5 + A^4 + A^3)B & (A^2 + A + I)B \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} u(kT_0) \\ u(kT_0 + 3T) \end{pmatrix} \\
\begin{pmatrix} y(kT_0) \\ y(kT_0 + 2T) \\ y(kT_0 + 4T) \end{pmatrix} &= \begin{pmatrix} C \\ CA^2 \\ CA^4 \end{pmatrix} x(kT_0) + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ C(A+I)B & 0 \\ C(A^3 + A^2 + A)B & CB \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} u(kT_0) \\ u(kT_0 + 3T) \end{pmatrix}
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

5.3. DRS Frequency Response

From a lifted LTI representation of a DRS, it is possible the calculation of the frequency response. The Theorem introduced in [10] says:

The output $y(k)$, when $u(k) = e^{j\omega T_u k}$, of a SISO dual-rate ($N_u T_u = N_y T_y$) lifted system $y_l(z) = G_{lifted}(z)u_l(z)$ is a collection of components $y_r(k) = \bar{y}_r e^{jT_y \omega_r k}$ of frequencies $\omega_r = \omega + 2\omega_y^s r / N_y$, for $r = 0, \dots, (N_y - 1)$, with $\omega_y^s = \pi / T_y$, and \bar{y}_r is given by:

$$\bar{y}_r = \frac{1}{N_y} \sum_{p=0}^{N_y-1} \sum_{q=0}^{N_u-1} G_{pq} (e^{j\omega_r T_y N_y}) e^{-jT_y \omega_r p} e^{j\omega T_u q} \tag{13}$$

AS it was proofed in [10], the discrete frequency-response computations are carried out by replacing $z = e^{j\omega T}$ for some T . It is easy to check that, from (13), the components will be given by the product of the frequency response of a left factor:

$$[1 \ z^{-1} \ z^{-2} \ \dots \ z^{-(N_y-1)}] G_{lifted}(z^{N_y})$$

replacing $z = e^{j\omega_r T_y}$, which gives a row vector, and the right factor (column vector)

$$(1 \ z \ z^2 \ \dots \ z^{N_u-1})^T$$

replacing $z = e^{j\omega T_u}$.

AS it will be explained later, there is a possibility of computing the whole frequency response from only one Bode plot in the case N_y and N_u are coprime. Note that, $\omega_s = 2\pi / (N_y T_y)$ and then that the components of the frequency response are defined at $\omega_r = \omega + r\omega_s$, for, $r = 0, \dots, N_y - 1$. For more details, see [10]

5.4. Frequency Response Interpretation

En esta seccion se debe hablar de la interpretacion de la respuesta en frecuencia. Basicamente que se obtienen N_y Bodes pero que solo su susma es la respuesta a T_0 computable con fasores.

As it is relatively easy to understand considering the equation (9) and unwrapping it, that is, doing the matrices prodcuts, an usually high dimension SISO transfer function is reached. This is a simple procedure but it produces a very unsatisfactory results as it will show later in this section. The results from the algorithm proposed in the previous section are proper but require a interpretation. From the results above, it can be tested that the DRS frequency response can be explained by adding $\frac{N_y}{gcd(N_u, N_y)}$ values from the Bode diagram outlined from 0 to $(\frac{N_y}{gcd(N_u, N_y)} - 1)N_u w_s$. In fact, for a input frequency b Rad/s, the output is the sum of senoidal signals with frequencies $b, b + N_u w_s, b + 2N_u w_s, \dots, b + (\frac{N_y}{gcd(N_u, N_y)} - 1)N_u w_s$ with amplitude and phase determined by Bode diagram at the indicated points. The coprime case is illustrative and gives a link with the theoretical results. If T_u and T_y are coprime, then, considering the blocks diagram from figure 5, the DRS frequency response is obtained reading the N_y points from the magnitude and phase Bode diagrams in the interval from 0 to $N_u N_y w_s$, each length $N_u w_s$.

The proposed algorithm introduced in [?] returns N_y Bode diagrams relatives to the tracks: 0 to $N_u N_y w_s$, $N_u w_s$ to $(N_y N_u + N_u)w_s, \dots, (N_y - 1)N_u w_s$ to $(N_y N_u + (N_y - 1)N_u)w_s$. So, the same Bode translated $N_u w_s$ N_y times is reached. Of course, the N_y points can be read in the interval 0 to $N_u w_s$ knowing the true sense of all of them.

In the sequel, a simple example is introduced illustrating the procedure. The academic system $G(s) = \frac{1}{(s+1)(s+4)}$ preceded by a zero order hold is considered, with $N_u = 2$ and $N_y = 3$ and a metaperiod $T_0 = 1$, that is $T_u = 0.1/2$ and $T_y = 0.1/3$. The DRS frequency response is composed by three components. The result is showed in figure 9. For this case, $w_s = \frac{2\pi}{T_0} = 6.28R/s$, $N_u w_s = 12.566R/s$ and $N_u N_y w_s = 37.699R/s$ As it can be seen, the Bode diagram is made up with three components which significance is achieved each $N_u w_s$. In fact and as it was said before, if the input is a senoid with pulsation $w = 3R/s$, the three components are:

Component	w (R/s)	Magnitude (dB)	Phase (Rad)
1	3	-24.8	-2.64
2	3+12.56=15.56	-65.85	2.96
3	3+(2*12.56)=28.3	-51.11	-1.275

in figures 10 and 11 it is explained graphically the procedure. If the sampling

Figure 9: DRS Bode

Figure 10: DRS Bode. $w = 3R/s$

times are coprime is possible to read in just one Bode diagram every value. This is the same that read the value of each component in its proper w and it is the same as well that read in the zone 0 to w_s but taking into account that the real value of the frequency of component i is $w + i \times N_u w_s$. Note the linear scale of the frequency axis in both figures.

At this point, it is time to check the goodness of the procedure. Adding the three responses, the result is equivalent to the output of the $ZOH - G(s)$ with the proposed input. As it can be seen in figure 12 the output true response is mapped at T_y at steady state.

However, the classical way, as it was said before, the problem is the high dimension of the transfer function that usually leads to an inefficient use of classical Bode computation routines. For explaining this problem some examples are introduced now. If the continuous-time system with ZOH

$$G(s) = \frac{20}{(s+1)(s+3)}$$

is considered, the results for a metaperiod $T_0 = 0.1$ $T_u = T_0/2$ and $T_y = T_0/3$

Figure 11: DRS Bode. $w = 3R/s$. Zoom

Figure 12: Output Components Sum Comparison

Figure 13: DRS Bode. Comparison of Methods

computed using both methods are plotted in figure 13. As it can see, the results from the procedure based on obtaining the transfer function show some disagree with correct ones.

The mistake is even greater if the degree grows up, considering for instance a metaperiod $T_0 = 0.1$, $T_u = T_0/4$ and $T_y = T_0/3$. Figure 14 plots this last case with unacceptable results.

6. Application

In this section the DR frequency response is applied to two different systems with different conclusions. The first is a continuous system which model:

$$G_{pm} = \frac{1.5}{(s + 0.5)(s + 1.5)}$$

is closed loop controlled by a serial PID,

$$u(t) = K_p \left[e(t) + T_D \frac{d}{dt} e(t) + \frac{1}{T_i} \int_0^t e(\tau) d\tau \right]$$

Figure 14: DRS Bode. Comparison of Methods

with $K_p = 8$, $T_D = 0.2$, and $T_i = 3.2$ in order to achieve some specifications. A discrete time PID controller approximation for a sampling period T , is given by [16]:

$$\begin{aligned} q_0 &= K_p \left(1 + \frac{T_D}{T} \right) \\ q_1 &= -K_p \left(1 + 2\frac{T_D}{T} - \frac{T}{T_i} \right) \\ q_2 &= K_p \frac{T_D}{T} \end{aligned}$$

Nevertheless, a multiplicative uncertainty has been assumed in the real system:

$$G_{pm} = \frac{1.5}{(s + 0.5)(s + 1.5)} \frac{10s + 1}{100s + 1}$$

that is, with a low frequency pole and high frequency zero. A single rate control, which is called "fast" is designed for $T = 0.1$. Due to diverse restrictions it is just possible to make the output measure every $T = 0.3$. With these conditions the DR and inferential control with $N = 3$ is planned. Now the three options are going to be compared. In figure 15 is depicted the closed loop step response for the three controllers designed for the model plant. In figure 16 has been considered the application to the real process (that is with model plant missmatching MPM). As it can be seen, the inferential control leads to a very slow output response, being the DR control response similar to the one of the fast single rate control. The Bode diagram explained before in figure 17 confirms this behaviour. Moreover, if the y/d Bode diagram is analysed, see figure 18, it is clear the ineffective disturbance rejection capability of the inferential control, while the DR control is valid for this purpose.

7. Conclusions

In this contribution the interpretation of a new, proper and efficient way to obtain the frequency response of a DRS was introduced. It is also tested that the other methods for computing the MRS frequency response: MRS MIMO consideration and transfer function obtaining leads to partial or unacceptable results respectively. Some examples are introduced with the intention to clarify the understanding and consequences of this new method. This tool allows to ask properly some practical questions about MRS.

Figure 15: DRS Bode. Comparison of Methods

Figure 16: DRS Bode. Comparison of Methods

Figure 17: DRS Bode. Comparison of Methods

Figure 18: DRS Bode. Comparison of Methods

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